

Deliverable 2.2

Scaling and Replication of Pilots

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Executive Summary

Coastal communities face many challenges including extreme weather associated with climate change, increased pressures from urban development and tourism, as well as changes in traditional and cultural practices. When faced with such a myriad of ever-changing challenges, it can be difficult to adapt. Recognising that these complex challenges require multiple, integrated solutions, EmpowerUs will support coastal communities to create multiple, integrated and flexible solutions to enable these communities to transition towards more sustainable, inclusive and resilient coastal development. Pilot interventions are a core part of the solutions being developed. This deliverable briefly outlines the pilot projects that will be implemented in the 6 EmpowerUs Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs) and, if they are successful, an initial mapping of strategies for pilot scaling and/or replication.

The TCLs have identified key issues related to the empowerment of coastal communities through a series of engagement, data collection, and reporting tasks. Each TCL hosted an initial workshop in Summer 2023, to engage community members and key stakeholders to determine initial needs and preferences for the development of pilot programmes. Each TCL also conducted a Governance Audit (Deliverable 2.1), which evaluated the governance environment specific to the TCL area. In Autumn 2023, each TCL hosted a second workshop, which engaged the participants in discussions about the selection of a pilot programme and ensured that the proposed pilots aligned with the priorities of each TCL area.

Within EmpowerUs, pilot programmes are small-scale projects that are designed to test new ideas and approaches before they are implemented on a larger scale. If a pilot programme is successful, it may be scaled or replicated. Scaling means that it is expanded to reach more people or to be implemented in a wider area. Replication, on the other hand, refers to the implementation of a successful pilot programme in a new context. Work Package 2 provided a template (Appendix 1) to the TCLs, to support the development of draft pilot programmes and to map out initial strategies for scaling and replication. The template asked the academic leads from each TCL to report key dimensions of their pilot programmes, including: details of the pilot programme, the expected impact, the capacity of the host / local partner organisation to implement the pilot, and how issues such as equity and inclusion would be considered within pilots. The 6 pilot programmes developed include the development of an ecotourism and ocean literacy brand (Bulgaria); coastal master planning (Cyprus); enhancing the appeal of traditional fisheries (Finland); a social enterprise support programme (Ireland); enhancing transport and connectivity for remote communities (Norway); and developing cross-sectoral collaboration for environmental protection (Spain).

If successful these pilot programmes may be scaled and replicated through several mechanisms, which are outlined in this report. Potential scaling processes include scaling out by broadening EmpowerUs' engagement and collaboration with government, non-government actors, additional stakeholders and the public to make the core aspects of the pilots available to others (Bulgaria, Finland, Ireland, Spain) and scaling up by accessing upcoming policy windows to seek to embed pilot ideas within emerging regional or national policies or to lobby for policy changes (Cyprus, Ireland, Norway). Replication processes may include working with others to replicate the pilot in other areas (Norway, Spain), including accessing additional funding (e.g. EMFAF) for replication (Finland) and working through the host organisation to replicate in other communities where they have a remit (Ireland). The final section of this report outlines how more detailed scaling and replication processes will be developed over the lifetime of the pilot programmes in each TCL.

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1. Introduction

A key aspect of the EmpowerUs project involves the development and implementation of pilot programmes. The pilots will test innovative approaches and interventions, which, if successful, could be scaled or replicated for broader implementation. Each Transition Coastal Lab (TCL) will implement and test at least one pilot intervention with their community. To implement their pilot, each TCL has an Empowerment Action Fund of €50,000, which is managed by the lead of each TCL.

A key aspect of scaling and replication strategies within EmpowerUs is the role of local partners¹ in each of the TCLs. EmpowerUs has been designed around the capacity of the local hosts to facilitate and implement bespoke pilot programmes and, if the pilots are successful, to mobilise scaling and/or replication processes within their organisation or network. It is, therefore, crucial to understand the competency of each local partner when reading the draft pilot programmes and their associated scaling and replication process in this document (see Table 1).

However, the successful transition from pilot to scaled-up program remains a significant challenge, often hindering the widespread adoption of promising practices and limiting their impact (Battista et al., 2017). To address common issues that may impede the potential to scale up or replicate successful EmpowerUS pilots, each TCL was asked to answer several issues when drafting their initial pilot programme idea (see Appendix 1 for template).

This document outlines:

1. A draft pilot programme for each lab, the issues it seeks to address, the overall socio-ecological transition envisaged within the pilots, and pilot aims and objectives;
2. The core activities of the pilot, including target audiences and how they will participate in pilot programme activities;
3. Potential barriers that may hinder the success of the pilot programme;
4. The capacity of the TCL partners to implement the pilot;
5. A draft budget and Gantt chart for each pilot;
6. How the pilot will empower local communities by acting on existing structural and/or agency issues, and how the pilot will address equity and inclusion;
7. An overview of the pilot's evaluation strategy; and
8. Potential scaling and replication mechanisms.

A brief overview of scaling and replication is provided in the next section. This is followed by a description of the draft pilot programme developed in each TCL. The document concludes by outlining the steps EmpowerUs will take to enable successful pilots to be scaled and/or replicated.

¹ In the Spanish TCL, UAB acts as both the academic lead and local host.

TCL	Local Host Partner	Functions
Bulgaria	Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation	BBF works to conserve biodiversity in Bulgaria and neighbouring countries, supporting the participation of citizens and local communities in managing natural resources and protected areas and raising public awareness on the issues of biodiversity and nature protection
Cyprus	Development Agency of Lemesos LTD	The purpose of ANELEM LTD is to develop the wider area of Limassol District through the management, maintenance and protection of natural and cultural resources, the introduction of innovation and entrepreneurship in the production system, the introduction and expansion of the use of renewable energy sources and social development.
Finland	The Fisheries Agency at the Government of Åland	Works to make sure that Åland's fisheries are competitive, economically profitable and socially sustainable. The stocks and ecosystems that are used by the fisheries are protected and cared for by the Fisheries Agency to make sure that there are high-quality products available for human consumption.
Ireland	Údarás na Gaeltachta (UnaG)	UnaG is the regional authority responsible for the economic, social and cultural development of the Gaeltacht (Irish-speaking regions). The Údarás funds and fosters a wide range of enterprise development and job creation initiatives and supports strategic language, cultural and community-based activities.
Norway	Kunnskapsparken Helgeland (KPH)	KPH aims to be a driving force for innovation, value creation and growth in Helgeland, Norway. The organisation works closely with business, public enterprises, research and educational environments. Their expertise is in competence, innovation, business establishment/incubation, clusters and networks.
Spain	Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB)	The Department of Social and Cultural Anthropology of the UAB is at the forefront of anthropological research and teaching in Spain. The department orients its teaching and research towards ethnographic studies in different parts of the world, towards the development of anthropological theory and knowledge. It focuses on the application of this knowledge to various social intervention programs in the field of cultural diversity, socio-environmental relations and health.

Table 1. Local hosts and key functions as they relate to EmpowerUs

1.1 Scaling and replication

The scaling up and replication of pilot programmes are important because they allow for the effective dissemination of evidence-based interventions. When a pilot programme is shown to be effective, scaling it up or replicating it can help to improve the lives of more people. Scaling up and replication of pilot programmes can be a complex and challenging process, but it is essential for the effective dissemination of evidence-based interventions. Gillespie (2004) has written about the complexities of scaling and replication in community-driven development, and his analysis provides insights with direct application to EmpowerUs' goals of supporting coastal community empowerment. Gillespie sets out a typology to understand scaling processes:

- Quantitative: Where a program expands in size, geographical base, or budget;
- Functional: Where a program increases in the types of activities and integration with other programmes;
- Political: Where a program increases in political power and engagement with wider political processes;
- Organisational: Where a program increases in organisational strength, including capacity building. (Gillespie, 2004, p. 8).

For this report, TCLs were asked to consider issues related to *scaling up*, i.e., increasing the functional, political, and organisational capacity of the pilot intervention, as well as *scaling out*, which focuses primarily on increasing the size and geographical footprint of the intervention.

Building on Gillespie's typology, Squires (2013) notes that there are both internal and external drivers which contribute to scaling processes, as organisations and initiatives are influenced both by the external contexts in which they operate as well as the internal dynamics of organisational structure and the agency of leaders and entrepreneurs (Squires, 2013). For this report, TCLs were asked: to describe the host organisation's capacity to implement the pilot, referring to any other projects and programmes that they are running that might assist the pilot or facilitate the continuation of the pilot post-project; and to outline any barriers to pilot implementation and scaling, including mapping actors that may not participate in the pilot but could have an impact on its success. Answers to both these questions will help inform scaling and replication strategies within each TCL (see Section 4).

Replication is a complex process due to the unique local contexts of a particular intervention. Understanding the contextual factors that enabled the successful implementation of a pilot intervention in one context and their presence or absence in another context is key to replication strategies. Exact replication is never possible as local contexts will shape the ultimate success or failure of a given intervention. The factors that lead to success are always grounded in the local context and can include dimensions such as the experience and commitment of the individuals involved, receptivity among local communities, and a favourable enabling environment (Squires, 2013). The dynamics of local contexts must be considered if a replication strategy is to be successful, and project leaders should consider factors such as financial systems, legal and regulatory frameworks, acceptability of the intervention to local stakeholders and community members, and access to technical support (Squires, 2013). Community-driven development should prioritise adaptation and learning through understanding local contexts over simplistic concepts of replication based on prior success in a given location (Gillespie, 2004). A detailed analysis of local contexts has been produced (D2.1) and this will inform replication processes if pilots are successful (see Section 4).

2. EmpowerUs Pilot Programmes

The EmpowerUs Project is concerned with the empowerment of coastal communities to enhance the environmental, economic and social sustainability of the areas. To examine the concept of empowerment, this work invited the TCLs to consider the impact of their proposed interventions on structural and agential issues in each of the lab areas. Equity and inclusion are core principles of EmpowerUs, and as such each TCL was asked to consider how their pilot intervention would include a focus on inclusion and equity to ensure meaningful empowerment throughout the TCL communities. This section outlines the draft pilot for each TCL, focusing on: TCL context; Pilot Solution; Budget; Empowerment; Host and Lab Capacity; Equity and Inclusion; Evolution; and Scaling and Replication.

2.1 Bulgaria:

Context

Atanasovsko Lake is a coastal lagoon located north of the city of Burgas. It is a part of the Burgas lakes complex, which is one of the three most significant wetland complexes for congregations of waterfowl along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast. The region of Atanasovsko Lake currently supports a total of 334 bird species. The lake is a Natura 2000 site (Special Protected Area and Site of Community Interest) with vital ecosystem functions, including as a key nesting and feeding habitat for birds on the Via Pontica migratory route. Parts of the lake are used for salt-making by traditional salt extraction techniques. Ocean literacy and civic engagement projects previously in place have shown that the lake can serve as a benchmark for nature conservation, local development, and service development.

Challenges and risks in this area include:

1. Pressures on the coastal ecosystem from urbanisation, tourism and coastal area development, including an increase in infrastructure, pollution and waste.
2. Extreme weather events prompted by climate change, such as disastrous floods damaging 30 per cent of salt-producing infrastructure, which led to decreased water salinity after intensive rainfall.
3. Changes in local livelihoods and culture - changing regional and national economic priorities, especially the emphasis on tourism as the coastal region's leading industry, have caused the withdrawal of private interest in harvesting salt through traditional means.
4. Wide variety of stakeholders with conflicting values and interests.

Social innovations co-produced by the consortium and Atanasovsko Lake stakeholders will help determine new ways of strengthening the lake's value to the local community and enhancing its ability to serve as a benchmark of sustainable development models on the Bulgarian coastline. The intervention will further emphasize ocean literacy and a tailored empowerment program that can enable the local coastal community to function as an empowered participant in environmental decision-making along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast.

Pilot solution

Pilot Name: "symBiotic" ecotourism & ocean literacy brand

There is a need for better citizen engagement in local governance; for a more diversified tourist/recreational offering in Burgas that can simultaneously draw a more diverse (tourist) audience, especially higher-paying environmentally conscious visitors and thereby provide better economic

opportunities for (young) locals; as well as a general need for higher levels of ocean literacy concerning climate change, the role of the Burgas wetlands for mitigation, and the value of the Atanasovsko lake more specifically. The community has also expressed a need/desire for better connectivity to the blue/green spaces to Burgas, as well as better accessibility (at least viewpoints) to the lake and special info centre for AL (the existing places do not serve in this capacity).

The pilot addresses the problems by proposing and implementing a series of ecotourism & ocean literacy offerings under the common “symBiotic” brand established with the BBF’s eponymous exhibition space, currently situated in the administrative part of the Salinas and comparatively close to the Atanasovsko lake. Better connectivity would be ensured at the new location by closer proximity to the Sea Garden park and through the opening of a view line to the lake and the sea and activities within the lake.

The pilot will also aim to reestablish the exhibition at a more permanent location, ideally on municipal land closer to both the Sea Garden and Atanasovsko lake, where it can expand and evolve into a visitors’ centre and event space for the Atanasovsko lake and associated ecotourist and ocean literacy activities.

Core activities:

- Procedural research on the possible pathways for identifying a permanent “symBiotic” location on municipal property – assessment of the two possible procedures, including their feasibility; likewise, procedural research on licensing “symBiotic” as a patented brand
- Citizen initiative committee / public launch meeting to be organized by BBF to gain publicity and support
- Legal steps to patenting “SymBiotic” as a brand
- Research and development for the activities under the brand throughout the pilot: events / courses / tours / food events
- Expansion and relocation of the symBiotic exhibition, public launch
- A series of events / courses / tours under the brand (if permanent location not secured, these are to be organized at various locations, including the “old” symBiotic space)

See the Gantt chart in the Appendix for details of the implementation plan.

Budget:

- Phase 1: €4,000 for technical assistance for the development of the new main symBiotic site, information campaign to support the new Atanasovsko Lake Visitor Centre and case visits.
- Phase 2: €30,000 for the relocation/construction and setting up of the new symBiotic main location - expected to be a light form construction (container/sustainable beach stand type).
- Phase 3: €2,000 to develop a business plan, plan activities, and access resources.
- Phase 4: €14,000 for the opening of the new symBiotic visitor centre for the 2025 season, social media development and OL activities, and the establishment of tours, activities, and events.

Empowerment

Expected impact of the pilot on structural issues within the TCL

- Strengthen the strategic role of nongovernmental organizations and citizen activism / initiatives in local development, including in the ecotourism industry and thereby in the blue economy
- Protect natural resources along the coastline by popularizing economic models that prioritize the sustainable use and development of the coast
- Improve the local community's ocean literacy and sociocultural link to both the sea and the wetland areas and lagoons around Burgas, including by promoting a better understanding of climate change impacts
- Promote cross-stakeholder cooperation around topics of sustainability

Expected impact of the pilot on stakeholder agency within the TCL

- By emphasizing knowledge building for ocean literacy and development for ecotourism offerings under an accessible and popular brand, the pilot will build the capacity of local organizations and the community itself to engage in the tourism sector specifically and the blue economy generally in a more environmentally, economically, and socially sustainable way
- The pilot will also strengthen the ability of the nongovernmental sector to capture value from the blue economy on the southern Bulgarian Black Sea coast
- Each of the chosen procedural approaches for requesting a long-term lease of municipal property, if successful, has the potential to improve stakeholder agency as a key outcome of the process of implementation itself:
- One of the two possible procedural approaches for this request involves implementing a local citizen initiative committee, a bottom-up democratic procedure in Bulgarian legislation that has received little attention and use since its establishment. Should the BBF implement it successfully, this would set a precedent for more common use amongst the citizen activists and the nongovernmental sector
 - (a local citizen initiative in accordance with the Law for Direct Citizen Participation in the National and Local Governance, Ch. III, Articles 46-53: this suggestion came from an engaged stakeholder who attended workshop 2 and is currently being researched by the team)
- The alternative procedural approach (direct request to the municipality after discussions with the mayor) would likewise, if successful, help reinforce institutional recognition for the key role played by nongovernmental organizations in Burgas and on the coastline, thereby improving nongovernmental and citizen agency

Host and lab capacity

The host has extensive experience with implementing long-term projects, including:

- A series of LIFE projects and their assets:

- Life for Burgas Lakes (2010 – 2013) <https://biodiversity.bg/en/LIFE-for-the-Bourgas-Lakes.p1247>
- Salt of Life (2012-2018) <https://saltoflife.biodiversity.bg/en/>
- Lagoon of Life project (2019 – 2024) <https://lagoon.biodiversity.bg>

Additionally, the host has strong expertise in developing and popularizing successful OL activities in the region, some of which have also partially engaged with the ecotourism / environmental products market:

- Existing SymBiotic space (an interactive exhibition with OL elements) which already gained recognition among Burgas citizens replicating elements of this model will be familiar to the community; established as a travelling exhibition with 13 locations along the country and more than 30,000 visitors;
- Developed and managed the Avocet trail at the Birdwatching hide of AL;
- Developed Educational programme for AL;
- Developed products with a cause that promotes nature conservation of AL and Burgas wetlands;
- Experts with expertise in interpretative methods for ecological education (project: Eurobird <https://biodiversity.bg/EuroBird-3-3876>)
- Expertise in wetlands management (organizing courses, training students, special guide for students)
- Developed Regional trademark “Strandja” for accommodation, places for food and attractions together with the Park Directorate;
- Organizing the Biodiversity Carnival with the Municipality of Burgas (12 editions) for children aged 4-10 years.

Finally, the host has a wide-ranging network that will help ensure the success of the pilot:

- Engaged supporters and volunteers from the civil society of Burgas;
- Strong connections to local and national institutions and media;
- Consultative Council for AL– established and socially recognised structure that has been adopted by the Regional Inspectorate of Water and Environment - Burgas;

Equity and inclusion

BBF is committed to providing a safe environment for all its employees, free from discrimination on any grounds and from harassment at work, including sexual harassment. The BBF team considers gender equality to be of great importance. As an employer, BBF has a strong track record in integrating women and young people into the labour market. The development of the pilot will apply all these

principles. As an additional equity and inclusion interest, the pilot will also look to involve elderly people in the community.

Pilot Evaluation

In Bulgaria, the proposed evaluation strategy will rely on semi-structured stakeholder interviews and follow-up Q-sorts to assess the reach and strategic effects that the Pilot has had over its duration. Since this methodology replicates the baseline governance audit conducted before the start of the pilot implementation phase, the second round of interviews and Q-sorts will help capture and demonstrate the extent to which the pilot has helped positively influence structures, agencies, attitudes, and thus community empowerment in general.

Scaling and replication

Scaling up: If successful in its establishment of a permanent location to serve as a hub of ecotourist activities, the pilot will help set a precedent for strengthening direct civic and nongovernmental participation in the urban and municipal planning process (regardless of the procedure chosen). If the local citizen initiative procedural route is implemented, moreover, this will set a strong precedent for utilizing the direct participation law in similar cases, which will be a direct scaling-up benefit.

We anticipate that the pilot's suite of ocean literacy and sustainable tourism activities (citizen courses, tours of the wetland areas, etc.) will be integrated through formal advertising channels into the municipal tourism landscape, including through collaborative work with the municipality. Success here opens up the potential for the pilot to help redress the local pattern of top-down approaches overtaking bottom-up entrepreneurship.

Scaling out: One concrete aim of this pilot is precisely the capacity of a wider set of activities and events under the symBiotic brand to reach a broader audience, thereby engaging even more (types of) stakeholders with the pressing themes of climate change mitigation, socio-ecological change on the coastline, the need for alternative economic models, and similar key themes and challenges identified throughout the governance audit process. Thus, the pilots' success by definition would mean a scaling out of benefits including networking with other actors, sharing practices, evidencing wider engagement with stakeholders who can effect change, as well as – especially if the local citizen initiative procedural pathway is implemented – formal coalition building for a more engaged democratic process.

Replication: The specific blend of ecotourist and OL activities that the symBiotic brand would offer could help establish a blue economy model that considers not only profit but also environmental and community well-being on the coast, something that could be replicated (with allowances made for geographic and cultural specificities) in other contexts.

Within Bulgaria, specifically, the example of a successful civic public (NGO) - institutional public (municipality) partnership that will necessarily underpin the pilot (especially but not only concerning the establishment of a permanent location), could prove to be another replicable benefit from the pilot. While similar initiatives of civic-public partnerships exist elsewhere, in Bulgaria they are relatively underdeveloped, and indeed Europe-wide their implementation is as of yet still limited. Success here could set an example that could be replicable elsewhere, especially in other coastal contexts.

2.2 Cyprus:

Context

The Cypriot TCL is comprised of three neighbouring communities which are situated in the Eastern Limassol region, along the south coast of Cyprus: Moni (population: 391), Monagrouli (population: 471), and Pentakomo (population: 644). Though these are coastal communities, there is a poor connection to the sea, as the core of the village and the housing zones are situated at the upper side of a motorway which was constructed in 1978 and is approximately 3 kilometres away from the coast.

Challenges and risks in this TCL include:

1. The communities are poorly connected to the sea, with a motorway (constructed in 1978) separating them from the coast that is only approximately 3 kilometres away.
2. Heavy industrialisation in the area between the communities and the coast, including a cement factory, a water and waste treatment facility, sites for building waste, an old power station and two quarrying zones.
3. Under-appreciation of the ecological importance of the area that is being further undermined by Governmental policies.

Pilot solution

Pilot name: Coastal Master Plan

The pilot will result in a co-created coastal Master Plan for the Eastern Limassol Region, specifically a master plan for the coastal area within the administrative areas of the communities Pentakomo, Monagrouli and Moni. The master plan will also include possible linkages between the core of the communities (at the inland side of the motorway) with the coastal area.

There is limited connectivity between the sea and the communities, both in terms of physical as well as psychological / emotive connectivity. There is also an under-appreciation of the ecological as well as cultural values of the coastal area at different levels, local, regional and national.

The pilot will engage the communities, as well as the broader society and users of the coastline and the relevant authorities to better understand and map, the ecological, social and cultural values of the area, and will explore how they can be portrayed and reflected in a coastal master plan. The process as well as the final outcome, particularly in the case that it becomes materialised (as separate sections or as a whole) will lead to an increase in the connectivity between the communities and the sea. In terms of the physical (actual) connectivity, the co-creation process will support the realisation of the importance of the area by the various stakeholders through the discussion, search and exchange of information for the various important elements. Additionally, an actual master plan will set the foundations for the horizontal as well as vertical connectivity of the coastal area as it will form the 1st phase of working towards the creation of walkways, cycling paths, nature paths, information points and other soft infrastructure in the area. The latest will support a broader societal appreciation of the area as it will raise its profile and attractiveness.

The pilot aims to support the sustainable recreational use of the coastal area of the Lab area in a way which highlights its ecological and cultural aspects through the co-creation of a coastal master plan. The target is that in the next decade, the different parts of the master plan will have the possibility to mature and acquire the funds to be implemented.

The core activities of the pilot include:

- Preparation of a coastal master plan by a consultancy firm. The following activities will support this process:
 - Participatory workshops for the identification of the ecological, cultural and social importance of the coastline.
 - Participatory workshops and surveys to collect ideas for smaller ‘interventions’ to be incorporated into the master plan.
 - Data collection from communities regarding previous projects or interventions planned in the area might help to incorporate into the master plan.
 - Workshop(s) with the local authorities to adapt the Master Plan to the legal framework.
 - A public consultation to receive opinions on the draft plan.
 - Submission of the draft plan.
- Identification of funding possibilities for the different interventions.
- Training program(s) / seminar(s) on project management for TCL Host.

See the Gantt chart in the Appendix for details of the implementation plan.

The target audience includes all users of the coastline, though there is a particular focus on local communities, as well as relevant public authorities. The aim is to allow for the involvement of as many stakeholders as possible, using a range of co-creation methodologies and consultation procedures. The ‘end product’ will be something which will be accessible and will aim to be used by all who have connections with the area or who are open to exploring and discovering new areas.

The overall socio-ecological transition we hope to achieve is two-fold. Firstly, through the process and discussions around the creation of the coastal master plan, it is hoped that the local communities will appreciate the coastal strip for its ecological and cultural importance and will be encouraged to protect it. Secondly, and in a synergistic manner, this will be reflected in the broader governmental strategy for the area, leading to the withdrawal of the plan to construct a marine aquaculture harbour in the zone adjacent to the newly created Natura 2000 area.

Budget:

- €1,000.00: Training program(s) / seminar(s) on project management for coordinator Styliana Charitou (TCL Host).
- €2,000.00: Budget for participatory workshops regarding the development of the Master Plan.
- €12,000.00: Coordination and management by TCL Host: this includes, among other, general coordination of the project, overseeing the proposal and deliverables, and preparation of tender documents (through the eProcurement system – Treasury of the Republic of Cyprus).
- €15,000.00: Preparation and finalizing of the general coastal master plan by a consultancy firm (urban planning team, land surveyor etc).

- €20,000.00: Preparation and finalizing studies and drawings regarding a specific area of the general master plan as the 1st phase of implementation. This includes all required experts such as architects, civil engineers, electrical engineers, mechanical engineers, topographers, quantity surveyors etc.

Empowerment

The discussions which took place during Workshop 2 between the participants highlighted the fact that there is room for understanding between members of the communities and some of the governmental authorities on some issues. Through the pilot, we hope to create more opportunities for discussions and to showcase the importance of dialogue and proper consultation. In the long-term, this will hopefully show a different kind of way of working to the competent authorities. Additionally, members of the communities will appreciate the more inclusive process and will start demanding for the creation of more participatory processes at various levels.

Through this pilot, the various stakeholders, especially the local communities and other users of the sea, will learn through the variety of participatory processes that they have a lot to gain through their increased participation in various processes. Community stakeholders already seem to be realising the possibilities offered through embracing their own agency in influencing the future of their communities, as well as the possibilities of creating a collective community agency.

Host and lab capacity

The TCL Host is the Development Agency of Limassol LTD, whose main purpose is the development of the wider rural area of Limassol District by contributing to the utilization, development, management, maintenance and protection of natural and cultural resources, the introduction of innovation and entrepreneurship in the productive system, the introduction and expansion of the use of renewable energy resources and the support and improvement of new collective structures and social development. In addition, the company is responsible for the Administration and Accounting support of the Organization of Integrated Waste Management Facilities Limassol and has more than 16 years of experience in implementing various National and European Programs. Examples of programmes running that shall assist the pilot and facilitate the current project are the Rural Development Programme "Leader", Interreg Balkan Programme, Life IP (Life IP CY zero waste) Programme and many more.

Both the TCL Host and the Academic Lead have good links with various stakeholders whose involvement in the creation of the master plan is important. Both organisations have experience in organizing consultations as well as participatory workshops to support the consultancy firm.

Moreover, the TCL Host manages the EMFF fund for the Limassol region. This experience of the TCL Host is ultimately extremely important as it can ensure that at least parts of the co-created masterplan can attain funding to materialize.

Equity and inclusion

As part of the pilot, a series of participatory planning workshops will be organised with a plan on how to ensure that the planning process for the master plan will be as inclusive as possible (including efforts to address gender issues). Additionally, since the 'end product', the master plan, will be something to be enjoyed by all members of the local communities, hikers, beachgoers, and all

current and future users of the sea, it is expected that there will be a high equity impact from this pilot.

Pilot Evaluation

A realist evaluation strategy will be developed in conjunction with QUB to evaluate the success of the pilot.

Scaling and replication

Scaling up: Through the pilot, we might identify local needs to support the participation of local communities, as individuals or collectives.

Scaling out: In the case of the Cypriot TCL, scaling up would offer particular methodological frameworks and processes for planning authorities to support mechanisms of inclusion to support sustainable coastal transitions. This could be particularly relevant as a local authority reform which is planned to come into force in May 2024 will create opportunities for new and more inclusive ways of planning.

Replication: Important contextual factors for the successful implementation of this pilot include the fact that the coastal area was undermined and thus a strategic and holistic approach was required to understand how there could be a reciprocal relationship between the area and the communities.

2.3 Finland:

Context

The self-governing province of the Åland Islands lies off the southwest coast of Finland. Åland is an autonomous, demilitarised, Swedish-speaking region of Finland. The autonomous status is laid down in this Autonomy Act and areas wherein the Åland parliament has the competence to legislate are laid down in Art. 18 of the Act of the Autonomy of Åland (1991/1144). All business related to internal affairs falls under the competence of the Åland parliament. The relationship between the Åland Islands and the EU is regulated in the Åland protocol, thus confirming the special status under international law.

The TCL Åland covers five municipalities in the north-northwest of Åland: Geta, Hammarland, Finström, Saltvik and Eckerö. They are described by the directors as ‘rural municipalities, safe and prosperous’. Eckerö, the most westerly situated municipality in Finland is also described as a major tourism municipality.

Challenges and risks in this TCL include:

1. Human-wildlife conflicts exist between recovering and expanding seal and cormorant populations and professional, household and recreational fishers. Major challenges for fishing are caused by the seal- and cormorant-induced losses and the inability of local communities to sufficiently mitigate these problems.
2. Conflicts exist between local stakeholder groups and wider interests and governance frameworks. For example, at the local level, management decisions in the fishing waters (managed by statutory fishery associations) are made by private water owners in 10 villages.

There are strict rules and regulations for recreational fishers' activities, with 10 different types of fishing permits for the area.

3. Hunting practices are a cause for concern for the inhabitants and recreational communities in the area.

Pilot solution

Pilot Name: The Åland fisheries appeal

The core issue to be addressed through the pilot is the declining fish populations and fisheries sector on Åland. This will be done by involving a broad fisheries community and filling gaps in data, science-based knowledge and giving an updated description of the situation.

The main aim of the pilot is to activate interest groups (especially water owners) to lift the fisheries sector before irreparable damage is 'done' (environmentally, economically, culturally, and socially) on the traditional Ålandic fisheries sector. The core activities of the pilot will include Workshops, Ocean Literacy, interviews, empirical studies, statistical data collection, and visualisation for the public and media.

The overall socio-ecological transition that this pilot seeks to advance is:

- To provide sustainable tools for the fisheries community and local water common members to govern the waters.
- To activate current non-active and non-local water owners, including women and youth, to care for water and fish resources.
- To secure a sustainable tourism and recreational fisheries sector and provide agency to the profession.

See the Gantt chart in the Appendix for details of the implementation plan.

Budget:

- €6,000: Updating the Neuman Fisheries report for Åland, 2000-2007 with a focus on the TCL area to show the decline in coastal fisheries.
- €10,000: Describe the 2023 fisheries sector and seal hunting practises on Åland. Also, provide historical data references. This evidence will be used to show the Ålandic fisheries' identity and change over time.
- €10,000: Statistical data gathering from the Statistical bureau of Åland ÅSUB on the tourism sector and fisheries. This will provide information on how the sector impacts the fish populations.
- €10,000: Map spawning areas, protected areas and fishing license areas in the TCL area. This will give an ecosystem-based approach to governance and show the important areas in need of protection. The protective measures can contribute to sustainable fish populations.
- €10,000: Communication - Embed the pilot locally within the water commons to provide them with tools for sustainable management to protect the fish stock and the fisheries culture on Åland.
- €4,000: Host 4 workshops, both webinars and in-person to keep stakeholders involved and engage more people.

Empowerment

Structural impact:

Ecosystem-based approach with cooperation across several small locally governed water areas.

Agential impact:

By involving the water commons and stakeholder groups, both formal and informal, in additional workshops we will ensure that there is impact on agency throughout the coastal community. Many stakeholders also own additional shares of water commons in other places around Åland so the impact will hopefully spread.

Host and lab capacity

As the local government through the fisheries agency acts as the host there are good capabilities to realise the pilot. Statistics are already being gathered on other activities in cooperation with ÅSUB (Statistical bureau of Åland), several other EU-funded projects are running within the organization focusing on biodiversity and there is a wide network of experts on different areas in-house. There is also an established cooperation with the Åbo Akademi university that can support the realisation.

Equity and inclusion

There are currently few women involved in the fisheries sector on Åland. By working closely with the water owners in the community we seek to engage female water owners who might not be very active in management at the moment but still have equal or more power in the formal governing of the waters by having a large share for example.

Youth, typically, do not own water on their own but we seek to engage them with OL activities and will write the invitations to future workshops in a way that persons who are invited know that it is vitally important to also invite active young people, elderly or others from the area that we might have failed to locate and invite.

Pilot Evaluation

For the Åland TCL, we suggest a multi-method approach to evaluate the pilot impact:

- We have already undertaken eight (8) Q samples before the pilot, to give an indicator of empowerment levels
- We will get a baseline and update previous data on the fisheries sector on Åland
- With the mapping of important spawning areas and restoration needs
- Innovative co-creation processes and possible barriers will be measured at the workshops with participative methods
- Measure how many and which actors (including gender, age, and background) have been involved in the EmpowerUs process at the beginning and the end of the pilot.
- Measure the area of water with a new management strategy.
- A second round of Q samples to measure people's attitudes regarding empowerment after the pilot.

Scaling and replication

Scaling up:

The strategy for scaling up the pilot is both by using knowledge-based tools like the planned reports but also by continuing the workshops that have led up to the pilot, spreading the word and getting people involved. Even though we focus on the TCL area in this project the situation is very similar all around Åland so activities that are well received have the potential of being picked up quite quickly and easily by other communities.

Scaling out:

A possible scale-out from the pilot could be to establish contacts with nearby regions in the Baltic sea facing similar issues. Water commons all over Åland could also apply for other funding, e.g. EMFAF, Leader, or equivalent, to expand the gathering of knowledge and conduct a similar mapping of their area to ensure sustainable development. Providing a co-creation process for local stakeholders to address difficult subjects with a lot of different aspects would be a scalable deliverable on its own and could apply to a multitude of issues along the coast.

Governance for water commons is legally regulated, hence, if the introduced governance tools work for the TCL commons, there is potential that scaling out can be used. There is also potential for other water commons or organizations to apply for funding elsewhere to replicate the interventions done within the pilot.

Replication:

Any pilot conducted on Åland is easily replicable within the Åland Islands since the community is fairly homogenous. Since the setting is different on Åland than our nearby regions especially when it comes to water ownership and direct management of many fish species, for example, any replication to other regions would probably have another local facilitator than water commons. However, the process of co-creation, gathering of data and placing it in a historical context could have great benefits in getting acceptance for interventions on a local scale.

Likewise, when it comes to formulating a common sustainability agenda in regard to fishing and the management of waters, both for cultural and biological reasons.

2.4 Ireland:

Context

The Irish Transition Coastal Lab (TCL) is focused on the coastal region of the Connemara and the Aran Islands, a largely rural area west of Galway City. Coastal Connemara is a location of inter-sectoral competition and changing demographics due to economic and industrial shifts in the region. Home to the largest Gaeltacht (Irish language-speaking community) on the island of Ireland, Connemara is a geographic region that has historically featured as a wild landscape with a distinctive history and culture and strong links to the Irish diaspora. The coast of Connemara is experiencing increasing pressures from Blue Growth, such as proposed aquaculture and energy developments. Tourism intensification on the Wild Atlantic Way (WAW), Blue Growth developments, and a strong sense of local identity have resulted in contestation over the future of coastal areas.

Challenges and risks in this TCL include:

1. Blue Growth pressures that displace local interests.

2. Emigration of young, highly skilled individuals from the region.
3. Low-skilled or seasonal employment opportunities.
4. Extractive forms of marine development, such as aquaculture.

Pilot solution

Pilot Name: Social Enterprise Support Programme

The pilot will involve a staged programme to develop the skills, knowledge and learning capacities of social enterprises and cooperatives operating in the Connemara Gaeltacht.

There is a need to capture wealth by and for the community from blue growth sectors on the Irish coast. The tourism and energy sectors are growing, but their environmental, social and economic effects are uneven and thus need to be prioritised as a community-based response. Population loss is, in part, encouraged, especially among young people, by a lack of local jobs that compete in salary terms with urban centres.

The community and voluntary sectors are strong at local organisation, but comparatively less developed in economic development. The pilot, therefore, aims to empower the community with the capacity to form, scale and sustain social enterprises and cooperatives where they make the best use of natural resources (the scenery, the sea and coastal landscape as well as wind and tidal power); convert value from marine sectors for community use; and build ownership of coastal assets for and by local people.

Pilot's aims/objectives/targets:

- To develop more commercially viable and financially resilient social enterprises and cooperatives.
- To build the skills, knowledge and learning capacities of social enterprises and cooperatives across the Gaeltacht.
- To develop inclusive forms of business development that protect and enhance the natural, cultural and community assets of the Gaeltacht.
- To create a stronger enabling environment for the social enterprise and cooperative sector in the Gaeltacht.

Phase 1 will be the development of an online, modular programme of knowledge building aimed at informing community and voluntary sector organisations about the potential of the social economy.

Phase 2 will support specific skills in competence areas including finance, business planning, asset management, legal implications of ownership and planning and local development. This will be in the form of a technical assistance programme to enable groups to develop projects via feasibility studies, marketing strategies, sectoral research, business plans and economic appraisals, legal and planning advice and specialist technical expertise in say energy regulation.

Phase 3 will engage focused learning via visits, lectures and access to resources for social entrepreneurs with high growth potential.

Budget:

- €10,000: Phase 1 - Knowledge web development and resource formatting.
- €30,000: Phase 2 – Skills: Technical assistance programme to support finance, investment readiness, feasibility, research and prototyping.
- €20,000 - Phase 3 – Learning: site visits, lectures, and access to resources.

See the Gantt chart in the Appendix for details on implementation.

Empowerment

Structural empowerment:

- The pilot aims to develop a Gaeltacht wide capacity-building programme that will address skills deficits in local economic development across the (indigenous) community and voluntary sector.
- Help to address unemployment, strengthen labour market integration and create new socially owned businesses.
- Protect natural maritime resources with economic models that prioritise the sustainable use of the coast.

Agential empowerment:

- The pilot will build the capacity (via skills, knowledge and learning) of community organisations with an interest in trading in (environmental) assets, goods and services;
- Strengthen the ability of the social enterprise sector to capture value from the blue economy in the Gaeltacht.
- Create a learning community where sharing knowledge, best practices and resources is a cultural value within the Gaeltacht social economy.

Host and lab capacity

Údarás na Gaeltachta and Queen’s University Belfast have the expertise, resources and networks to organise, coordinate and evaluate the delivery of the pilot.

Údarás na Gaeltachta

- Business Support Programme including finance (grants and loans); premises; and technical support. <https://udaras.ie/en/business/>.
- Access to the G-Tech Digital Hub network to support the growth of social enterprise in communication and information technologies. <https://udaras.ie/en/business/gteic-digital-hubs/>.
- Integration with the social enterprise support programme. The Pilot can help underpin this broader initiative which in turn, can scale and sustain the interventions on capacity building. <https://udaras.ie/assets/uploads/2019/10/Straite%CC%81is-Fiontair-Sho%CC%81isialta-BE%CC%81ARLA-Web.pdf>.

Queen’s University Belfast

- ENSGOV research unit will integrate and support the research in its programme of work on environmental governance, local economic development and marine spatial planning. <https://www.qub.ac.uk/schools/NBE/Research/ResearchCells/>.
- Queen's Communities and Place is a dedicated research unit supporting community wealth and area based social economies. <https://www.qub.ac.uk/sites/qcap/>.

Equity and inclusion

The social economy has a strong track record in the labour market integration of women, young people, people with disabilities and migrants. The approach aims to support organisations with resources to better align services, facilities, access and formal employment with the needs, aspirations and capabilities of those furthest from the labour market.

Pilot Evaluation

In Ireland, we propose to use baseline and exit surveys with social enterprises and cooperatives; detailed analysis of the financial strength of the social enterprise sector over time; case studies of participating community businesses; and structured stakeholder interviews to assess the strategic effects of the Pilot and priorities for the future, especially in scaling and mainstreaming the approach within Údarás na Gaeltachta.

We are, therefore, interested in the way in which the Pilot can scale and develop the social economy and in the context of the realist design see a number of hypotheses, although these are best thought of as a set of propositions, likely relationships or interventions with specific effects. For Ireland, for example, these include:

- A stronger network of social enterprises will strengthen the power of local people to take greater control over their coastal environment, economy and social futures.
- Social enterprises can develop and deliver sustainable services in demand-deficient areas in dispersed coastal communities.
- Strengthening the skills, knowledge and learning capacity of social enterprise is critical to start-up, scaling and consolidation of the sector across the Connemara Gaeltacht.
- Social enterprises can capture larger and more sustainable forms of value from the blue growth economy.
- The enabling environment around legislation, finance, technical support, policy and programme investment is key to the creation of an alternative coastal economy.
- Community participation: community legitimacy expressed as governance control accountability and participation in decision-making processes are prerequisites to the development of a fair and sustainable coastal social economy.

Scaling and replication

Scaling up:

We aim to achieve functional change by developing the social finance environment, such as strengthening the ability of credit unions to lend to social enterprises; developing procurement via social value legislation in public sector contracts; and introducing community asset transfer to enable social enterprises and cooperatives to access coastal assets including state-owned land and property. Údarás will be critical, as a state agency, in accessing politicians, officials and sector representatives to lobby for change. The research evidence from the pilot will be a vital instrument in this respect.

Given the emphasis on power, local elected representatives (Council, Regional Assembly and nationally) will be vital to target. Here the media would need to be more engaged, story based and build a 'constituency' case for further support. Clearly defined requests, such as a technical assistance budget, grant investment, support for Údarás and so on could be part of this agenda. Supporting the host, via the TCL, should be a cross-cutting objective in EmpowerUs.

Scaling out:

The pilot will have scope effects by expanding into other Gaeltacht areas enabled by Údarás na Gaeltachta as our host. Sharing the learning with Gaeltacht managers and development staff will enable the seamless transfer of practice, especially via the Irish language. We also want to scale out into high-growth sectors via social innovation strategies and in a practical sense, through the G-Tech network. Implementing appropriate technologies to strengthen the use of Nature-Based Solutions (energy prosumption, for example) would be a significant development opportunity for the wider sector.

Replication:

A key aspect of replication is the need to build the institutional infrastructure to enable rapid sharing of best practices and knowledge across the social enterprise sector. The Údarás social enterprise strategy is one area for development, especially to explore how a stronger network might build a social economy ecosystem for the Gaeltacht. Cascading out to other coastal (and rural) communities would be a logical extension of such a community of practice.

2.5 Norway:

Context

The Træna TCL is a municipality in Nordland County, Norway. It is part of the Helgeland traditional district. The administrative centre of the municipality is the island/village of Husøya. There is also a population center on the island of Selvær, and two inhabitants living on Sanna island. The main industries in Træna are fishing and processing, tourism, and aquaculture. Træna is a dynamic community with a 9000-year history. Current demographic and industrial changes bring challenges and opportunities for the Træna community.

Challenges and risks in this TCL include:

1. High overturn of inhabitants causing issues with inclusion and continuity in public services.
2. Vulnerable and limited transportation.
3. Few facilities/amenities/experiences for tourists.
4. Housing shortages with high costs and low resell values.

Pilot solution

Pilot Name: Attractive Træna

Træna is part of an inter-municipality project along with two other island municipalities. All of these communities have challenges with transport infrastructure and connectivity to the mainland. Our pilot

has two objectives: Firstly, in collaboration with these municipalities, we need to map the current transportation system and see if there are alternative ways of solving these challenges. There are already indicators that there are different ways to handle poor communications as in the example of the helicopter route on Værøy. Secondly, we want to come up with strategies to improve these conditions using current solutions in a different manner or structure.

Træna is located far out to sea. There are two ways people can be transported out to the islands; either by speedboat or by ferry. The speedboats are often cancelled during the winter months and the ferry only goes twice a day. Poor communications are issues that can hinder people moving to Træna, or businesses developing. With an emerging tourism development on the island, there is a sense of urgency to improve communications so that local businesses can continue developing themselves.

The pilot aims to explore different solutions which might be possible to implement within the structural limitations of Norwegian transportation policy and examine alternative innovative ideas which might improve the current challenges for all three of the participants of the Island-Municipality-Project. The mapping of new solutions would also include an analysis of how other municipalities have made successful changes to their transportation solutions sustainably, and which values they have gained as a result of these solutions.

By mapping new solutions for the current transportation solutions and examining alternative transportation we will strengthen the municipality's capacity to influence the county and possible private stakeholders necessary to change the current transportation method or structure/organization of it. The mapping will also allow the municipality to make an updated and visualized roadmap/schedule which they might use both for inhabitants travelling back and forth from the mainland, and for tourists – thus solving their challenges regarding the poor understanding of the transportation system/routes, and possibly have a positive effect on the islands attractiveness as a place to live, work and visit, and decrease the out-migration of youth.

To develop a knowledge report on innovative transportation solutions/policies for these island communities. The report will include a mapping of current transportation schedules, options and correspondence, and an analysis of new transportation solutions. This information might give the municipality a better understanding of how they might exploit the current solutions and make it possible for them to develop an illustration which might be used for communicational purposes, such as mentioned in part 2.

By using information from similar case studies which have implemented new solutions, the report will give the municipality more information about how these options might affect municipalities' attractiveness, availability, and value creation, and emphasize whether they are more or less sustainable than the current options. It will also make it possible for the municipality to develop a strategy as to how they might go about changing the current solutions, especially regarding structural changes which need to be done by influencing the county to change policies or allocate funds for new solutions.

- Develop solutions addressing these challenges and connect these to the overall strategic plans for all of the municipalities in the project.

- Do a qualitative survey as to whether or not new transportation solutions are sustainable; cost of using the new solutions, frequency of using it, environmental impact, other purposes than transporting humans to and from the mainland, whether or not the inhabitants will use it etc.

Budget:

- €5,000: Phase 1 – Knowledge Report
- €15,000: Phase 2 - Conference
- €30,000: Phase 3 – Testing Solutions

See the Gantt chart in the Appendix for further details.

Empowerment

Potential structural impact:

The pilot aims to develop a knowledge report on possible new transportation solutions for all three island municipalities – it is a knowledge building program that would enable the municipality to take the most effective measures in dealing with poor transportation issues.

There will also be suggestions for measures to improve the situation. It is a co-creation pilot with all relevant actors responsible for transportation policies in Norway. Investment booms, as we have seen in neighbouring island communities, tend to create improvements in the structures due to growth. This pilot aims to enhance this improvement for all relevant actors.

Potential agential impact:

The pilot will build capacity via skills and knowledge: thought providing the municipality with knowledge about different transportation solutions and thus providing the municipality with the knowledge needed to advocate for structural change in the county, through providing the municipality with knowledge about existing solutions they might strengthen or make visible for the public.

Host and lab capacity

The KPH has a vast portfolio of relatable projects. This pilot can be planned and implemented in close collaboration with NRI, UFZ and the different levels of stakeholders identified in question 5. Here are some of the projects KPH is involved with: <https://www.kph.no/prosjekter/>

Equity and inclusion

A very broad spectrum of stakeholders has been participating in the workshops leading up to the selection of the pilot. Similarly, a major challenge like transportation, will impact all people in Træna - gender, age, ethnicity etc.

The solutions are aimed to be publicly available, and thus create value for the municipality, inhabitants, local businesses and tourism.

Pilot Evaluation

For the Træna TCL, we suggest a multi-method approach to evaluate the pilot impact:

- Firstly, we have already undertaken Qs to give an indicator of empowerment levels
- Secondly, we need to get a baseline of the transportation situation of all three islands

- Information from Visit Helgeland, the county of Nordland etc.
- Thirdly, ethnographic fieldwork of the innovative co-creation process and possible barriers
- Fourthly, interviews with stakeholders on Træna before and after pilot implementation. The first part has already been undertaken.
- Fifthly, testing the baseline with new transportation numbers and activities related to the pilot process.
- Sixthly, last Q method to measure people's attitudes regarding empowerment

Scaling and replication

Scaling up:

If successful, the county may use the Træna-case to advocate for national change of accessibility regarding for example the schedules and layover duration and examine if it is possible to look at connecting routes throughout Nordland County and other counties bordering Nordland.

The county of Nordland has already been present in workshop 1 to better understand EmpowerUs' co-creational methodologies. By continuing this co-creational process with them about communications may change how they produce policies, and in these collaborative processes, the policies may be changed. The regional transport plan has just recently been updated and is due to be updated in 2033. However, due to the large investments in the region and a clearer emphasis on tourism, these strategies might need to be updated sooner.

Scaling out:

A successful improvement of the policies and practises of the transportation sector in the region sustains the blue growth that goes on there. Both on Træna and Lovund local companies invest large sums of money – much of this due to the Salmon farms in these two places. When tourism is set to explode on the scene with both hotel and the development of tourist products there will be additional needs for more transportation. It is a cumulative effect, which we have seen in other places. As such, one might argue that there is potential for scaling out scenarios due to this pilot. As several of the existing transportation solutions already is connected to several municipalities located nearby, the solution will benefit more than just the Træna community.

Replication:

This project can easily be replicated in other political/administrative contexts. In many regions in Norway, municipalities are already involved in inter-municipal collaboration. By learning these co-creational methodologies and also knowledge building regarding transportation innovation such clusters of municipalities can readily replicate the process. As the structural changes needed for this change lie within the county, it makes the process easier for other municipalities within the county to replicate the solutions. The whole of Northern Norway struggles with a lack of connectivity regarding public transport. This is also the case for hot spots of tourism like world famous Lofoten. Public transport is poorly coordinated and the booking solutions difficult. In a transition towards a more environmentally sustainable tourism development, public transportation needs to be greatly improved. As of now people visiting Lofoten mainly use their own cars or mobile homes. As such, co-creation projects on transportation where policymakers, businesses, researchers and other NGOs come together and try to find solutions are needed in the region.

2.6 Spain:

Context

Cap de Creus is a peninsula on the Costa Brava in northeastern Catalonia, Spain, belonging to the province of Girona and the region of Alt Empordà. Its rugged coastline and rocky cliffs make it a popular attraction. In 1998, it became the Natural Park of Cap de Creus due to a social demand from the territory to preserve its exceptional natural and cultural heritage, including historical landmarks and archaeological sites. Cap de Creus is one of Catalonia's largest natural parks, encompassing the peninsula (11,000 ha) and its surrounding marine area (3,000 ha). The region's coastline is home to a diverse range of marine life, making environmental conservation a top priority for its inhabitants. As Spain's first marine-terrestrial natural park, the community faces challenges in balancing space use while defending social and ecological interests. At the maritime coastal forefront, The Park Natural of Cap de Creus comprises four villages, Roses, Cadaqués, El Port de la Selva, and Llançà, whose currently tourism-based economy replaced in the 2nd half of 20th century the traditional fishing and horticulture, progressively displaced as subsidiary activities.

Challenges and risks in this TCL include:

1. Anthropogenic impacts from fishing and recreational activities (e.g. recreational fishing, artisanal fishing, diving, recreational boating) result in a decline of marine living resources, damage to the seabed and fragile marine habitats, endangering biodiversity and the socio-economic development of marine resource-dependent livelihoods.
2. Climate change impacts on fish species and biodiversity exacerbating tensions between maritime activities (fishing, recreational fishing, and scuba diving) competing for the same spaces and resources.
3. Increase in recreational activities and a decline in artisanal fishing, due to the large number of tourists visiting the area, leading to conflicts between stakeholder groups.
4. Climate change effects such as changes in the weather, distribution, and abundance of species, the appearance of warm-water species, and weaknesses of coralligenous communities have altered fisheries and may affect tourism activities dependent on biodiversity.

Pilot solution

The pilot project will consist of an initiative to facilitate the networking of resources, knowledge and capabilities of the marine protected area of Cap de Creus to enhance cross-sectoral network (tourism operators, MPA managers, conservationist entities and associations) collaboration in the sustainable development of the blue economy.

Issues to be addressed through the pilot:

- Blue economy growth (over-tourism, offshore wind farm projects in fishing-restricted areas for ecosystem recovery, overexploitation of aquatic living resources) is undermining the protection goals of the declared marine protected area in 1998.
- The lack of agreement between economic sectors in the plans of use and regulation of the marine protected area does not allow the implementation of the protection targets.

- The tourist sector, and all the blue economy activities, in general, must be aligned with environmental protection goals fostering responsible environmental behaviour and attitudes.
- Erosion of ecosystem services is threatening traditional livelihoods and the tourism industry dependent on the seascape and the richness of marine biodiversity and cultural heritage.

How does the pilot address this problem?

The Cap de Creus community is very proactive, involved in projects, volunteer initiatives, cooperatives and activism for environmental protection and social development, but has little decision-making capacity in the environmental management bodies of the administration in the face of the blue economy growth. The pilot will empower the community by facilitating synergies to strengthen eco-social networking initiatives, giving them visibility and the ability to influence environmental management through multistakeholder cooperative platforms for the dissemination of values, practices and certification, allowing local reappropriation of the use and management of resources and the alignment of the blue economy with the biodiversity.

What are the pilot's aims/objectives/targets?

- To involve social fabric businesses and visitors as social agents of change for the protection of the environment and the improvement of social resilience. By transferring people about environmental assets for their welfare, helps them to make decisions on the environment they want to ensure respect for their need for a sustainable environment.
- To engage the tourism sector for the promotion of the beauty of the sea in a responsible way, to transfer knowledge to general society (locals and visitors) as well as the conservation principles to be respected.
- To give value to the natural and cultural diversity –with gender perspective- of the community as economic assets to benefit from ecosystem services under conservation principles
- To promote a transformative model towards eco-social practices in the tourism sector that may foster inclusive job opportunities, diversification and future opportunities for alternative income generation.

What are the core activities involved in the pilot (e.g. training events, plan development workshops, citizen science data collection etc.)? Please also complete the pilot Gantt chart in the Excel provided.

- Phase 1 will identify local supports to develop a hub of sustainable blue economy through a multistakeholder collaborative platform, logistics, technical assistance, availability of resources and potential support for its long-term maintenance
- Phase 2 will identify through multistakeholder collaboration the scientific knowledge, local community knowledge, and main conservationist principles approved for the Uses and Management Master Plan of the Cap de Creus as potential paramount values to foster eco-social practices and environmental behaviours according to the protection goals.
- Phase 3 Organization of two-side (digital and physical) engagement actions and tools for the implementation of transformative eco-social practices in the blue economy. The two-side engagement actions won't be launched simultaneously. First, it is expected to launch the digital one, and second the physical one.

Who are the target audience for the pilot and how will they participate in it? What will you do to recruit participants?

- Social and environmental initiatives, entities and associations, environmental and social projects
- Local businesses from the touristic sector, enterprises of cultural heritage promotion, and tourism cooperatives from the area of influence of Cap de Creus
- Volunteer table at Cap de Creus, NGOs.
- Parc Natural de Cap de Creus managers as a delivery agent in volunteer and socio-environmental initiatives support.
- Municipalities and Municipalities dependencies (e.g. tourism office)
- Fishers
- Local trader's associations

We will recruit them in person and by phone, visiting them and arranging appointments. They took part also in each of the WSs.

What is the overall socio-ecological transition what you hope to achieve through the pilot?

- Ensuring community decision-making capacity of influence on environmental management for its welfare and the need for a sustainable environment
- Implementation of effective assets to navigate towards socio-ecological transformative changes in the blue economy aligned with conservationist criteria and nature-based solutions (MPA).
- Strengthen the touristic industry, livelihoods, and potential alternative incomes that might be generated by the sustainable eco-social tourist sector
- To guarantee the implementation of the Uses and Management Master Plan of Cap de Creus Marine Protected Area according to the conservationism principles, and nature-based social and economic purposes
- Boosting pro-environmental behaviour, attitudes and actions

What are the potential barriers and/or pitfalls that the pilot may have to address?

- Engaging the community (fishers, entities and associations, MPA managers, NGOs, municipalities, and local businesses) is paramount for the creation, and implementation of the Hub, its long-term maintenance and scaling up to all the Natural Park of Cape de Creus. Our pilot is only focused on the Marine Protected Area (3.064 ha), but the entire Natural Park comprises also terrestrial protected areas (10.780 ha).
- The success of the digital Hub is dependent on the campaign and the involvement of the community and touristic sector promotion at the local, regional, national and even international level
- Final approval of the Uses and Management Master Plan expected by the end of 2023 may influence the community involvement and motivation
- Opposition of economic sectors with economic power and political influence

Besides the target group who will participate in the pilot, who are the other local actors that will have to be informed about the pilot? How will you do this? Please refer back to the stakeholder analysis that you conducted for D2.1.

- Local Trader's Associations
- Local tourism cooperative
- Hospitality industry
- Tourist operators at regional, national and international levels

UAB with the support of the Natural Park Managers and communitarian social fabric will support knowledge transfer to the necessary social actors.

UAB have the expertise, resources and networks to organise, coordinate and evaluate the delivery of the pilot.

Budget:

Digital platform: 25.000-35.000€

Physical platform: 10.000€

Campaign of divulgation: 600€

See the Gantt chart in the Appendix for details on implementation.

Empowerment

Expected impact of the pilot on structural issues:

- To help implement the conservation objectives of the Marine Protected Area
- Promote cultural diversity with a gender perspective and diversity of knowledge systems as a social and economic asset balanced with conservation objectives.
- Lay the groundwork for a real transformation of the tourism sector, providing the structure for eco-social tourism practices, which could generate new income and diversification of economic activities.

Expected impact of the pilot on stakeholder agency:

- Empower the multi-stakeholder community capabilities to achieve wellbeing
- Strengthen community influence in decision-making for the management of the marine protected area.
- Strengthen the transformational potential of the community by joining forces, exchanging and sharing initiatives, knowledge and actions for change
- Capacity building to involve larger social groups of sea users at different scales (local, regional, international).

Host and lab capacity

UAB act as academic lead and host organization:

- UAB hosts a UAB business incubator to support the development of innovation and transference

- The Natural Park of Cap de Creus manages a table of volunteers and social media resources on socio-environmental projects that are available
- Entities and associations will provide resources for the digital and physical hub
- A consortium with all municipalities from the Cap de Creus is foreseen to be established for the long-term maintenance of the Hub
- The Autonomous University of Barcelona is in the process of establishing an interdisciplinary marine social science research effort that will support research programs on marine governance, knowledge systems, small-scale fishing, seafood systems, and marine protected areas.
- UAB, social anthropology, will be able to give support in marine social science to the projected Marine Research Center (Centre de la Mar) to be established in Roses thanks to the agreement with the Spanish National Research Center and University of Vic.

Equity and inclusion

Environmental wellbeing is one of the fundamental principles of environmental justice which implies cultural diversity -under gender perspective- integration into conservationist principles. Equity and inclusion ensure a balanced human-environment relationship which is implicit in eco-social practices of human activities.

Pilot Evaluation

We propose collecting semi-structured interviews with key social agents; to evaluate the Digital data of the use of the certification test; structured surveys to assess the overall strategic impact of the Pilot, to identify gaps, needs, and potential improvements for the future

We expect to reach a larger number of stakeholders and to escalate the digital side of the Pilot to produce an escalating transformation on environmental attitudes and behaviours, coastal and sea use and its protection.

- Strengthening the multistakeholder cooperative platform in the network will empower local people to take greater control in the environmental management decision-making, over the economy and future developments.
- Giving value to the diversity of cultural knowledge as social and economic assets makes coastal communities more resilient in front of environmental challenges
- Multistakeholder cooperative platform may put into practice sustainable values for the development of a blue economy
- The local reappropriation of the use and management of the environment is key for ensuring environmental equity and justice and avoiding undue privatization and sea grabbing that favour large companies to the detriment of small producers and users of the sea.
- Ensures community participation, involvement and co-responsibility in achieving the objectives of conservation, welfare and community rights.

Scaling and replication

Scaling up:

We expect to empower the Cap de Creus coastal community to make effective transformative changes in fishing, tourism practices, and social relations with the environment. Community will get power through practices and actions that can scale transformative changes at different levels fostering pro-

environmentally sustainable conception and relationship with the marine environment. Digital platform of stakeholders' actions engagement through volunteer and the co-creation processes of society (visitors and locals) in the divulgation of values, boost the responsible way to relate with the environment that may seed potential for transformation. This model of the expansion of initiatives and exchange networks is “fractal” rather than cumulative, although the vision of change through the aggregation of individual quotidian practices is also potentiated. The creation of coalitions through the multistakeholder cooperative platform will drive collective transformation. The involvement of local authorities (city councils, management bodies) will be essential to obtain more support in future instances.

Scaling out:

The pilot will have a pull effect by building bridges between initiatives, actions and projects that will engage stakeholders in environmental responsibility. The gamified digital certification will be an innovative and attractive format for disseminating environmental values, knowledge and conservation objectives that can be scaled geographically and reach a broad social sector. It is expected that, particularly, young people, as strong potential users of the digital platform, will be able to help network the pilot.

Replication:

It is expected a replication effect of the Pilot within conservationist communities and marine protected area networks (e.g. MedPan). In that way scaling out to other regions and international communities for the protection of the environment. The digital platform will be in different languages (Catalan, Spanish, French, English and German) to overcome possible linguistic barriers and take into account that the Natural Park of Cap de Creus has an international spotlight since it receives visitors and hosts migrants from different nationalities. Following a cascade effect, the pilot could be replicated in other marine protected areas and natural parks and become a larger support of networking protection and conservation.

3. Next steps: enabling conditions for scaling and replication

EmpowerUs will launch the pilots described above in March 2024. There is no guarantee that the pilots will be successful or that they will be scalable or replicable in the ways TCL have outlined above. However, by carefully planning and implementing scaling-up and/or replication processes, EmpowerUs will be prepared to exploit successful pilots. We outline below how the project will address key enabling conditions to ensure any successful pilot can be scaled and/or replicated.

Several enabling conditions need to be considered when planning scaling and replication processes, including

- **Resources:** Scaling up or replicating a pilot programme requires significant resources, including financial resources, human resources, and logistical resources. It is important to assess the resources that will be needed and to develop a plan for securing those resources. EmpowerUs TCLs have been provided with access to significant resources to implement pilot programmes (WP2) and to exploit their results (WP6). The draft pilot programmes will be refined and launched in March 2024. The launch of the pilots coincides with the first revision of EmpowerUs' Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, including Communication Activities (PDEC) (D6.4) and this provides an opportunity to further develop our initial scaling and replication strategies. Mid-term and final pilot evaluations will be conducted on each pilot, with the outcomes informing EmpowerUs' scaling and replication processes, and our final revision of our PDEC (D6.5, due M36).
- **Context:** The context in which a pilot programme is implemented can have a significant impact on its success. When scaling up or replicating a pilot programme, it is important to consider the differences between the pilot context and the new context. For example, the new context may have different demographics, different cultural norms, or different institutional structures. Each TCL has conducted an audit of local contexts (see D2.1) and will reference this when developing scaling and/or replication strategies. Furthermore, the pilot evaluation process (T3.3) will draw on realist evaluation methodologies which emphasize the importance of context, recognizing that interventions operate within specific social, organizational, and cultural environments.
- **Capacity:** The organizations that will be responsible for scaling up or replicating a pilot programme need to have the capacity to do so. This includes having the necessary skills, knowledge, and systems in place. This may involve providing training, technical assistance, and other support. EmpowerUs has been designed around local host partners who are well-placed to implement and scale these pilots. However, part of the pilot evaluation process (T3.3) will focus on this issue and feed into scaling and replication strategies.
- **Evaluation:** Conducting a rigorous evaluation of the pilot programme. This will help to determine whether the pilot programme is effective and whether it is scalable or replicable. Working with the TCLs, WP2 will develop an evaluation framework to monitor and assess the pilot interventions, using a realist evaluation approach. Realist evaluation is a robust approach to evaluating pilot programmes, providing a comprehensive understanding of how and why interventions work, for whom, and under what conditions. It goes beyond simply assessing outcomes to delve into the underlying mechanisms that drive program effectiveness. Realist evaluation offers a valuable approach to evaluating pilot programmes, providing in-depth insights into the mechanisms of change, contextual factors, and the conditions under which

interventions are likely to be effective. This knowledge is crucial for refining program designs, informing implementation strategies, and making informed decisions about scaling interventions to wider contexts.

- **Engagement.** It is important to engage with all stakeholders who will be affected by the scaling up or replication of the pilot programme. This includes beneficiaries, government officials, community members, and other organizations. Each TCL has already developed good relationships with local stakeholders and pilot implementation will include processes to engage other key actors and those who may help scale or replicate the pilot. The revised PDEC will provide an opportunity to further develop these engagement strategies.

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Appendices

Appendix 1 D2.2 Reporting Template

Lab Name:	Pilot Name:
Draft Pilot idea	<p><i>You should describe the overall pilot here:</i></p> <p><i>And then also answer the following question:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>1. What is the problem(s) to be addressed through the pilot? Developing a clear problem statement is very important. Avoid conflating the problem statement and the pilot. For example, a good problem would be 'There is a lack of affordable housing in Dingle'. A poor problem state would be 'we will develop a housing association to address the housing shortage in Dingle'.</i> <i>2. How does the pilot address this problem?</i> <i>3. What are the pilot's aims/objectives/targets?</i> <i>4. What are the core activities involved in the pilot (e.g. training events, plan development workshops, citizen science data collection etc.)? Please also complete the pilot Gantt chart in the Excel provided.</i> <i>5. Who are the target audience for the pilot and how will they participate in it? What will you do to recruit participants?</i> <i>6. What is the overall socio-ecological transition what you hope to achieve through the pilot?</i> <i>7. What are the potential barriers and/or pitfalls that the pilot may have to address?</i> <i>8. Besides the target group who will participate in the pilot, who are the other local actors that will have to be informed about the pilot? How will you do this? Please refer back to the stakeholder analysis that you conducted for D2.1.</i> <i>9. Who from EmpowerUs will lead and participate in implementing the pilot and do they need any training before launching the pilot in March 2024? If so, how and when will this training be undertaken?</i>

Capacity of host organisation to implement the pilot	<i>Here you should describe the host organisation's capacity to implement the pilot, referring to any other projects and programmes that they are running that might assist the pilot or facilitate the continuation of the pilot post-project.</i>
Budget	<i>Describe here your initial ideas for how the €50,000 development fund will be spent to support and implement the pilot.</i>
Potential structural impact	<i>Describe the expected impact of the pilot on structural issues within the TCL</i>
Potential agential impact	<i>Describe the expected impact of the pilot on stakeholder agency within the TCL</i>
Equity and inclusion	<i>Describe the expected impact of the pilot on gender, equity and other inclusion issues in the TCL</i>
Evaluation strategy	<i>QUB will help you answer this section using the realist evaluation approach. <u>*As we noted we will work with you to help articulate these across the Lab areas.</u></i>
Scaling, replicating and adapting the pilot	<p><i>How might the pilot be scaled, replicated or adapted? Key concepts include:</i></p> <p><i>For D2.2 we would like you to reflect on:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>1. Scaling up: this refers to activities that aim to change policy, rules, laws or practices so that they facilitate the sustainable implementation of the successful interventions. For example, if a citizen science intervention was found to produce reliable data about the condition of coastal ecosystems, scaling up could focus on changing marine governance regimes so that this form of data was deemed useable by marine management organisations. Scaling up in this instance might focus on developing a robust citizen science data validation process within the marine management organisation itself.</i> <p><i>The types of strategies that could be used for scaling up your pilot include: New policy development, partnering with similar interventions or projects, developing an advocacy strategy focused on legal change or refocusing institutional resources (especially financial investment).</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>2. Scaling out: this refers to the increasing the number of people or communities that benefit from an intervention. For example, a successful community housing association could be scaled out by accessing additional capital to enable it to purchase more housing stock.</i>

	<p><i>The types of strategies that could be used for scaling out your pilot include: networking with other actors including building formal coalitions, sharing practice and evidence of ‘what works’ lobbying stakeholders who can effect change and so on.</i></p> <p>3. <i>Replication: refers to activities that aim to spread the intervention geographically or to new contexts. Understanding the contextual factors that enabled the successful implementation of a pilot intervention in one context and their presence or absence in another context is key to replication strategies. For example, a housing association pilot may have been successful in context A as the financial rules around lending to community groups were very favourable. This does not mean that the pilot would necessarily fail in context B if the lending rules were less favourable. It means that any replication strategy would have to take this into account and seek to develop alternative funding support mechanisms in context B.</i></p> <p><i>The types of strategies that could be used for pilot replication could focus on dissemination and diffusion activities, incorporating critical assessment of the enabling conditions in the receiving context, co-production or collaborative workshops across contexts, etc.</i></p> <p><i>It is also important to look at how replication and scaling processes need to adapt the lessons for other areas. Not everything will work in another region or problem environment so what do you think might need to change to strengthen transferability</i></p>
<p>Operationalising scaling, replication and adaptation</p>	<p>* Note that you can develop specific aspects of scaling to populate the three areas above. You can see how we have used these areas to develop our own scaling strategies. Not all will be relevant, but again, we can support your thinking here.</p> <p>As we are interested in community <u>empowerment</u>, and the extent to which the pilot can strengthen the capability of coastal communities to shape the development of the coast. In scaling strategies, the pilot then needs to consider its relevance to other areas, issues, policy priorities and sectors. This involves thinking through a range of possibilities which, as an illustration only, might include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Scope</u> or sometimes called ‘scaling out’ so that the programme expands in size, geographical base, or budget;

- Mainstreaming, which is the way in which pilot interventions have been integrated, adapted or adopted (potentially via the TCL host) as formal programmes, spending programmes or policy interventions;
- Functional, involving increases in the types of activities and integration with other programmes, policies, regulatory instruments and legislative change;
- Political, involving increases in political power and engagement with wider political processes, recognition for issues, areas or communities; building stronger political alliances and ‘ways in’ to decision making systems;
- Capacity, which involves increases in community organisational capacity, skills, knowledge and a technical competence to act;
- Institutional that might include community networks, formal coalitions, integration with other organisations and sectors outside the Lab area as well as at different decision-making scales;
- Technological means broadening or implementing appropriate technologies or complementary activities to strengthen the use of Nature Based Solutions and inclusive local planning approaches; and
- Viability is a check to see how interventions supported via the Pilot can be sustained as well as putting in place resources (organisations, people, finance) to diffuse learning and influence policy and practice.

Appendix 2 Bulgaria Pilot Gantt Chart

Pilot Activity	Jan-24	Feb-24	Mar-24	Apr-24	May-24	Jun-24	Jul-24	Aug-24	Sep-24	Oct-24	Nov-24	Dec-24	Jan-25	Feb-25	Mar-25	Apr-25	May-25	Jun-25	Jul-25	Aug-25
Procedural research	█	█																		
Launch Event / Committee Meeting			█																	
Marketing/social media				█		█	█		█	█			█	█		█	█	█		
Patenting "SymBiotic" as brand				█	█	█														
(Collection of signatures)				█	█															
R&D - tour(s) / activities / space					█	█	█													
Eco-tour AL/wetland areas launch							█													
Submit request to municipality								█												
Food event @SymBiotic								█												
OL community training									█											
Municipal response received										█										
Mid-term review											█									
Preparing new exhibition												█	█	█						
OL community training															█	█				
Launch new exhibition																	█			
Eco-tour AL cont'd																	█	█	█	
Evaluation																		█	█	
Policy Brief																			█	█
Final Pilot Event																				█

Appendix 3 Cyprus Pilot Gantt Chart

Pilot Activity	Jan-24	Feb-24	Mar-24	Apr-24	May-24	Jun-24	Jul-24	Aug-24	Sep-24	Oct-24	Nov-24	Dec-24	Jan-25	Feb-25	Mar-25	Apr-25	May-25	Jun-25	Jul-25	Aug-25
Training program(s) / seminar(s) on project management for coordinator	█	█	█																	
Pilot Launch Event			█																	
Preparation of the general coastal master plan by a consultancy firm			█	█	█	█														
Participatory workshops regarding the development of the Master Plan				█	█	█														
Finalizing the general coastal master plan by a consultancy firm						█	█	█	█	█										
Mid-term review										█										
Evaluation																				
Policy Brief												█			█	█	█			
Preparation of studies and drawings													█							
Participatory workshops													█	█	█					
Finalizing studies and drawings															█	█	█	█	█	█
Final Pilot Event																				█

Appendix 4 Finland Pilot Gantt Chart

Pilot Activity	Jan-24	Feb-24	Mar-24	Apr-24	May-24	Jun-24	Jul-24	Aug-24	Sep-24	Oct-24	Nov-24	Dec-24	Jan-25	Feb-25	Mar-25	Apr-25	May-25	Jun-25	Jul-25	Aug-25
Pilot Launch Event			█																	
Activity workshops to visualise				█										█						
Activity statistical data gathering				█	█	█														
Activity fisheries and seal hunting update						█	█	█	█	█										
Activity review Neuman report			█	█	█															
Activity webinars						█			█											
Mid-term review										█										
Evaluation												█	█	█						
Policy Brief							█							█						
Final Pilot Event																				█

Appendix 5 Ireland Pilot Gantt Chart

Pilot Activity	Jan-24	Feb-24	Mar-24	Apr-24	May-24	Jun-24	Jul-24	Aug-24	Sep-24	Oct-24	Nov-24	Dec-24	Jan-25	Feb-25	Mar-25	Apr-25	May-25	Jun-25	Jul-25	Aug-25
Pilot Launch Event																				
Online Training Course																				
Technical Assistance Programme																				
Networking Events																				
Best Practice and Learning																				
Thematic Technical Papers																				
Mid-term review																				
Evaluation																				
Policy Brief																				
Final Pilot Event																				

Appendix 6 Norway Pilot Gantt Chart

Pilot Activity	Jan -24	Feb -24	Mar -24	Apr -24	May -24	Jun -24	Jul -24	Aug -24	Sep -24	Oct -24	Nov -24	Dec -24	Jan -25	Feb -25	Mar -25	Apr -25	May -25	Jun -25	Jul -25	Aug -25
Developing pilot	█																			
Establishing steering committee		█	█																	
Pilot Launch Event			█																	
Examine existing transportation		█	█	█	█	█														
Examine innovative solutions		█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█								
Stakeholder meetings with transportation-companies		█				█						█					█			
Developing map/illustration for current transport								█	█	█										
Examine permits and structural regulations regarding transport options	█	█	█			█	█	█												
Workshop with local stakeholders											█									
User Survey					█															
Developing prototypes																█	█	█	█	█
Mid-term review											█									
Evaluation															█	█				
Policy Brief																	█			
Final Pilot Event																				█

Appendix 7 Spain Pilot Gantt Chart

Pilot Activity	Jan -24	Feb -24	Mar -24	Apr -24	May -24	Jun -24	Jul- 24	Aug -24	Sep -24	Oct -24	Nov -24	Dec -24	Jan -25	Feb -25	Mar -25	Apr -25	May -25	Jun -25	Jul- 25	Aug -25
Identification of Knowledge, and main conservationist principles	█	█																		
Identification of local supports	█	█																		
Pilot Launch Event (digital platform)			█																	
Creation and adjustment of pilot (digital platform)	█	█	█	█	█	█														
Digital platform testing				█	█	█	█	█												
Organization of Physical pilot launch event: participants and workshops	█	█	█	█	█	█														
Physical pilot launch event									█	█										
Mid-term review (physical platform)										█	█	█								
Data gathering and review of digital platform										█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
Evaluation											█	█	█							
Policy Brief											█									
Final Pilot Event																			█	█

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